
Flux-driven transformations in open systems revisited - crystallization of amorphous Ni-P driven by reaction with Sn

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Abstract

An unexpected example of Flux-Driven Transformation in an open system is treated. Namely, the transformation of amorphous solution Ni-P into crystalline Ni₃P with simultaneous formation of the regular array of elongated voids during reaction with tin-based solder is treated as the discontinuous precipitation in an open system driven by the out-flux of Ni to reaction with Sn. The corresponding model predicts the lateral grain sizes of Ni₃P, phase volume ratio, and time law of reaction with exponent 1/3.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper is about the fundamental concept of Flux-Driven Phase Transformations (FDPT) in open systems and about some applications of this concept, in particular, to one of the problems of diffusion barrier instability in soldering. Namely, we suggest (for the first time, to the best of our knowledge) the theory and analytical model of the crystallization of amorphous alloy Ni-P initiated by reaction with tin-based solder. In Introduction we first formulate the basic ideas of Flux-Driven Transformations concept and shortly remind the phenomena which are well described in the frame of this approach (1.1). Then we describe the main experimental peculiarities of continuous electroless nickel transformation into sponge-like porous crystalline compound Ni₃P, simultaneously with formation and growth of intermediate compounds Ni₃Sn₄

and Ni_2SnP in the contact zone with solder (1.2) . We finish Introduction section with indication of two close fields - dealloying by selective etching with porous material formation, and porous individual nanoparticles and nanowires production by solid-state reactions (1.3). In Section 2 we suggest the geometrical scheme of our model and take into account the matter conservation constraints. In Section 3 we suggest the analytical model of Flux-Driven Discontinuous Precipitation predicting the very reasonable characteristic sizes of the emerging porous structure and kinetics of its growth.

1.1. Concept of Flux-Driven Phase Transformations.

Common first-order phase transformations in closed systems (like the decomposition of binary alloy in the thermal bath with fixed uniform temperature under fixed uniform external pressure) typically consist of nucleation of individual precipitates (of some solid solutions or ordered compounds), growth of these precipitates, and (the last stage) coarsening (ripening), if the main operating mechanism is bulk diffusion. On the other hand, if the temperature is low enough so that the bulk diffusion is frozen but diffusion via grain boundaries and inter-phase interfaces is operating, an optimal way for the alloy to decrease its Gibbs free energy is a Discontinuous Precipitation (DP) with formation and growth of lamellar colonies due to interdiffusion along moving transformation front. Driving forces and kinetics of the mentioned processes in closed systems are well studied [1-3]. Much less evident is our understanding of phase and structure transformations in open systems. Georges Martin et al studied the driven (globally homogeneous) alloys under irradiation or ball-milling [4-6]. They used the ballistic jumps frequencies (alongside with thermally activated jumps) within the master equation approach, and introduced the concepts of nonequilibrium phase diagrams and effective temperature.

Much less we understand, so far, about phase and structure transformations within globally inhomogeneous open systems under external fluxes with the non-zero divergence of the external flux of one or several components. First of all, here we mean the solid-state reactions at the solid-solid, solid-liquid, or solid-vapor interfaces. These chemical phenomena, from the physical point of view, should be treated as the

sequence of competing phase transformations (for example, formation and growth of ordered compounds) in the highly nonuniform systems (under sharp concentration gradients) proceeding under conditions of flux divergence (when in-flux is not equal to out-flux). This flux divergence becomes a reason and kind of additional driving force of phase transformation. In this case, all common stages of phase transformation become “Flux-Driven” and acquire, as a rule, the properties, very different from the case of closed systems. Few examples, analyzed by one of the authors of this paper (AG) jointly with K.P.Gurov, K.N.Tu, F. Hodaj, et al:

1.1.1. Flux-Driven Ripening (FDR) [7-9]. Growth of Cu_6Sn_5 scallops during a reaction between copper and tin-based liquid solder proceeds simultaneously with ripening (coarsening). During this process, the total surface area of the hemispherical scallops array remains constant (instead of minimization in common ripening), and the total volume increases (instead of tending to constant in common ripening). The rate of ripening, unlike the common Lifshitz-Slezov-Wagner (LSW) theory of Ostwald ripening in closed systems, is proportional to the flux of Cu via the liquid channels remaining between scallops due to the full wetting of high-angle boundaries between scallops by the liquid solder. On the other hand, the channel width is proportional to the combination of surface tensions [9]. If, by chance, the channels solidify, or flux across the reaction zone disappears due to some other reason, then the FDR stops. At that, the common coarsening driven by the minimization of surface energy may proceed further, but much slower. Theory [7-9], especially with an account of improvements made in [8,9], matches experimental data well.

1.1.2. Flux-Driven Grain Lateral Growth (FDGG) during thin film deposition [10]. While in previous case of FDR the “external” flux, responsible for driving of ripening, was a diffusion flux via the molten channels between grains, here the “external flux” is a deposition flux from vapor phase, and this external flux changes the kinetics of grain growth in thin film. During the deposition of thin single-component film with bamboo (columnar) structure the evolution of lateral grain sizes distribution may proceed by two mechanisms. First is typical grain growth along the whole height of the deposited film from the top to the bottom of the grains-columns,

driven by the difference of curvatures between the neighboring grains and corresponding differences of chemical potentials due to the Gibbs-Thomson effect. The second effect is a Flux-Driven Grain Growth, proceeding only at the momentary surface of the film during the time of one-atomic-layer deposition, depending on the deposition rate and realized via the “mushroom effect” at the contact lines between grain boundaries and the film surface: atoms arriving to the vicinity of the contact line from the vapor phase, have the opportunity of choice and larger probability to join the more favorable grain.

1.1.3. Flux-Driven Grain Lateral Growth during reactive phase growth with bamboo (columnar) structure [11,12]. In this case as well, at least two modes of grain growth are possible. The first mode is a normal grain growth along the whole length of each grain column (along the thickness of the growing intermediate phase). The second mode is an FDGG similar to the film deposition case, proceeding only at the joints of grains with interphase interfaces. Here the role of deposition flux from the previous example is played by the interdiffusion flux along the grain boundaries of the growing phase.

1.1.4. Flux-Driven Nucleation [13-15]. Nuclei of the future intermediate compounds are born at the interfaces and from the very beginning they let the diffusion fluxes pass through them or their boundaries. It leads to temporal suppression of some critical nuclei and growth of other stable or even metastable phases (intermediate phase growth/suppression criterion).

1.1.5. Flux-Driven Cellular Precipitation during transformation of Cu_6Sn_5 into spongy Cu_3Sn [16,17]. In [16,17] reactions in the sandwich-like sample "Cu-liquid Sn-Cu" lead at first to the formation (after consuming all liquid solder for reaction) of the solid sandwich-like system " $\text{Cu}-\text{Cu}_3\text{Sn}-\text{Cu}_6\text{Sn}_5-\text{Cu}_3\text{Sn}-\text{Cu}$ ". After this, the evolution of Cu_6Sn_5 changes drastically: Atoms of tin become sucked out to the sidewalls, presumably to react with the copper columns after some surface diffusion, according to [16], or (alternatively) to react with some unknown reagent in the surrounding flux according to Panchenko et al [18] (who discovered the sponge-like Cu_6Sn_5 phase formation). In both mechanisms, tin is migrating out of the Cu_6Sn_5 layer

by the surface diffusion via the percolating net of nano- and micron-size voids appearing as a result of decomposition of Sn-deficient Cu_6Sn_5 into " Cu_3Sn +voids spongy structure".

1.2. Transformation of amorphous Ni-P into crystalline Ni_3P with regular elongated voids. [19-30].

Crystallization of electroless Ni (amorphous solid solution of P in Ni) initiated by the reaction with tin-based solder, is a well-known problem in materials science [19-28]. Amorphous Ni-based alloy with phosphorous is used as a barrier between Cu and liquid solder, to prevent the fast growth of Cu_6Sn_5 scallops. Yet, due to the reaction of Ni with tin in solder, Ni is taken out from the amorphous alloy to react with Sn and form the bamboo-structured compound Ni_3Sn_4 . Fast diffusion of Cu along the boundaries of this new-formed structure leads to the formation of Cu_6Sn_5 caps over the barrier layer. Thus, the crystallization of electroless nickel makes this barrier non-effective. Here we have simultaneously two effects: First, the out-flux of Ni makes the content of solid solution closer to stoichiometry 3:1 and therefore increases the driving force of the crystallization of amorphous alloy into crystalline Ni_3P with a change of composition to stoichiometric value. On the other hand, simultaneously, the out-flux of Ni atoms generates supersaturation with vacancies. Therefore, the amorphous solution becomes unstable as well with respect to pores formation. The above-mentioned two factors (effective supersaturation with P and actual supersaturation with vacancies) should lead to simultaneous decomposition into compound Ni_3P and voids. It looks like such decomposition may proceed mainly via diffusion along the moving transformation front and have the features of discontinuous (lamellar) precipitation. Since this process is initiated by the reaction of Ni with external component Sn and by the flux of Ni towards the place of this reaction, one may call this process a Flux-Driven Discontinuous Precipitation (FDDP). Somehow, a more or less self-consistent theoretical description of electroless Ni crystallization driven by Ni out-flux is lacking (to the best of our knowledge).

In Ni(P) crystallization story, we seem to have a picture similar to the flux-driven

transformation of Cu_6Sn_5 into spongy Cu_3Sn under out-flux of Sn : in our case, Ni is sucked out of Ni(P) by the reaction with tin, and this out-flux leads simultaneously to void formation and to the formation and growth of columnar Ni_3P grains with free surfaces being used as the fast diffusion paths for Ni migration. The phase separation with the formation of quasiperiodic regions of Ni_3P and voids proceeds due to diffusion along the moving interface Ni(P)/(Ni_3P +voids layer), and it makes it similar to discontinuous precipitation. Based on our experimental observation, the voids, initially have a width of less than 10 nm, eventually, connect and form the free surface of the Ni_3P crystals (Fig. 1). After long time solid-state thermal aging, this layer has columnar grains of micron-size (Fig. 2). On the other hand, contrary to discontinuous precipitation in closed systems, in our case the interdiffusion along the interface is connected with and even generated by the outflux of Ni along the void surfaces to the reaction front with Sn to form Ni_3Sn_4 (and, to some extent, also a ternary phase Ni_2SnP). Moreover, the emerging phase has a fixed composition of compound Ni_3P . Thus, we have three peculiarities of discontinuous precipitation:

- (1) One of the emerging phases during precipitation is a "phase of emptiness" (quasiperiodically situated elongated voids).
- (2) Second emerging phase is a compound Ni_3P with definite composition (due to stoichiometry), contrary to discontinuous precipitation of solid solution in which the composition should be somehow optimized.
- (3) Precipitation is driven by the diffusion and reaction of Ni with the third component (Sn) outside the precipitation zone.

FIG. 1. TEM showing voids in the Ni_3P layer formed during reaction between an

electroless Ni-P alloy and Sn-3.5Ag solder after (a) 180s reflow at 250 °C (b) reflow at 250 °C followed by aging at 150 °C for 100h. The elongated voids are along the Ni diffusion direction.

(a)

(b)

FIG. 2. FESEM image of a) Columnar Ni₃P grains exposed on the fractured surface after the solder joint was pulled to failure [26]. b) Cross-sectional view of a fractured interface of the electroless Ni-P/Sn-3.5Ag solder joint aged at 200 °C for 100 h. The micron-sized columnar Ni₃P grains are clearly revealed. In both images, the arrows indicate the diffusion path.

1.3. Related problems of the porous structures formation.

Note that the just discussed porous Ni₃P formation has much in common with dealloying by selective etching, also leading to formation of porous materials [31-34]. Within our concept of the flux-driven processes in open systems, dealloying by etching may be treated (at least partially) as a flux-driven decomposition, but without formation of ordered compound, as in our case.

Another phenomenon, related to porous structures evolution, is a formation of individual hollow compound nanoparticles or nanowires during solid-state reaction with external medium. Pores are formed under condition of different mobilities of components within the newly formed phase during reaction. Namely, an outflux of the faster component with subsequent vacancy supersaturation and Kirkendall voiding [35-38], is another partial analogue of FDDP, described in this paper. In both of indicated

phenomena the Gibbs-Thomson effect and instability become important.

II. GEOMETRICAL SCHEME AND MATTER CONSERVATION CONSTRAINTS

The observed morphology of the spongy structure of the Ni_3P layer indicates that the mechanism of electroless nickel crystallization may be similar to the formation of the abovementioned spongy structure in Cu-Sn-Cu reaction - out-flux-driven decomposition of Ni(P) into " Ni_3P +voids" structure.

To give an idea of the mechanism, let us first consider the transformation of solution $Ni_{90}P_{10}$ in Fig. 3. Out of each 100 atoms (90 atoms of Ni and 10 atoms of P) 30 atoms of Ni and 10 atoms of P form the compound Ni_3P , and the rest (60 atoms of Ni) go out and migrate further along the free surface of the just formed Ni_3P grains-columns towards the reaction with Sn to form eventually the Ni_3Sn_4 compound.

FIG. 3 Scheme of lamellar zone formation by out-diffusion of Ni.

FIG. 4 Scheme of components redistribution along the interface in FDP at an arbitrary initial molar fraction “c” of phosphorous in the starting material.

Let us start with conservation law irrespective of kinetic parameters but bear in mind the following geometric picture: Let V be the instant velocity of the moving transformation front. To the left of this front, the material is in the parent state (solid solution or amorphous phase $Ni_{1-c}P_c$). Within the moving front, we have (like in typical cellular precipitation) redistribution along the front leading to the following morphology behind the front: columns (in our 2D model - lamellae) of a stoichiometric compound Ni_3P of some width $a = (1 - f) \cdot \lambda$ and columnar (in our 2D model - lamellar) voids of some width $b = f \cdot \lambda$, where λ is a “mean period” of spongy lamellar two-phase structure “ Ni_3P +voids”, f is a fraction of voids within Ni_3P layer.

2.1. Evaluation of the voids fraction within the Ni_3P phase layer

Let us first try to “predict” the ratio $f = \frac{b}{a+b}$ (fraction of voids within Ni_3P layer) using the very rough and, strictly speaking, incorrect assumption of Vegard law validity,

prescribing constant atomic volume to all atoms and vacancies in any phase state. Details then can be illustrated by Fig.4: Let N^{total} is the total number of atoms in some layer of height $\lambda/2$, thickness Δx , and width W ($\frac{\lambda}{2} \cdot \Delta x \cdot W = N^{\text{total}} \cdot \Omega$) of electroless nickel before the transformation. The bottom part of this sub-layer $\frac{a}{2} \cdot \Delta x \cdot W = (1 - f) \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2} \cdot \Delta x \cdot W$ transforms into compound Ni_3P of the same height $\frac{a}{2} = (1 - f) \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2}$ (if we neglect the atomic volume changes during transformation). The upper part with height $\frac{b}{2} = f \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2}$ is just dismantled via surface lateral diffusion:

- (1) all Ni atoms from this part ($\Delta_1 Ni = f \cdot (1 - c) \cdot N^{\text{total}}$) migrate further via surface diffusion along the free surfaces of Ni_3P columns to react with Sn and to form a Ni_3Sn_4 compound;
- (2) all P atoms from this part ($\Delta_1 P = f \cdot c \cdot N^{\text{total}}$) go to the bottom part and substitute the Ni atoms in the parent phase transforming it into a compound Ni_3P ;
- (3) The substituted atoms of Ni from the bottom part, the amount of which is equal to the amount of the coming P atoms ($\Delta_2 Ni = \Delta_1 P = f \cdot c \cdot N^{\text{total}}$) also migrate out of the interface solution/ Ni_3P (along axis Y) and further along the free surface of the columns Ni_3P (along axis X).
- (4) Then the ratio of Ni and P atoms in the new-formed compound Ni_3P (which should be 3:1, according to stoichiometry), on the other hand, may be expressed as

$$\frac{(1-f) \cdot (1-c) \cdot N^{\text{total}} - \Delta_2 Ni}{(1-f) \cdot c \cdot N^{\text{total}} + \Delta_1 P} = 3 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{So that } 3 = \frac{(1-f) \cdot (1-c) \cdot N^{\text{total}} - f \cdot c \cdot N^{\text{total}}}{(1-f) \cdot c \cdot N^{\text{total}} + f \cdot c \cdot N^{\text{total}}} = \frac{(1-f) - c}{c}, \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow f = 1 - 4c \quad (2)$$

Thus, if, for example, $c=12.5$ at.% of phosphorous then, neglecting the volume relaxation, one might expect 50 percent voiding within the “ Ni_3P +void” layer. Note that the experimentally observed fraction of voids might be less, due to the effects of volume relaxation.

2.2. Evaluation of the phase thicknesses ratio (so far neglecting the formation of the ternary Ni-Sn-P phase)

Let us predict the ratio of thicknesses of the two growing reaction layers - a layer of the compound Ni_3Sn_4 and the layer of compound Ni_3P together with incorporated voids. So far, we neglect the formation of the ternary phase which usually remains rather thin till the full consumption of electroless Ni. Then we may obtain the results just using the mass conservation law, without any additional kinetic arguments.

Let v be a number of moles of $Ni_{1-c}P_c$ reacting with an unknown number of moles v_2 of Sn to form simultaneously the unknown number v_y of moles of Ni_3Sn_4 and with another unknown number v_x of moles of Ni_3P with voids inside. Thus,

Three conservation laws for three components Ni, P, and Sn give the following set of algebraic equations:

$$v(1 - c) = 3v_x + 3v_y, \quad vc = v_x, \quad v_2 = 4v_y. \quad (4)$$

Solution of this set gives:

$$v_x = c \cdot v, \quad v_y = \frac{1-4c}{3} \cdot v, \quad v_2 = \frac{4}{3} \cdot (1 - 4c) \cdot v. \quad (5)$$

The volume of the Ni_3Sn_4 phase layer is then

$$V(Ni_3Sn_4) = \frac{(3M_{Ni}+4M_{Sn})}{\rho_{Ni_3Sn_4}} \frac{1-4c}{3} \cdot v. \quad (6)$$

The volume of the Ni_3P phase is

$$V(Ni_3P) = \frac{(3M_{Ni}+M_P)}{\rho_{Ni_3P}} c \cdot v. \quad (7)$$

The ratio of Ni_3Sn_4 volume and Ni_3P volume will be

$$\frac{V(Ni_3Sn_4)}{V(Ni_3P)} = \frac{4\rho_{Ni_3P}(3M_{Ni}+4M_{Sn})}{3\rho_{Ni_3Sn_4}(3M_{Ni}+M_P)} \frac{(1-4c)}{4c} = 3.9 \cdot \frac{(1-4c)}{4c} \approx \frac{(1-4c)}{c}. \quad (8)$$

FIG. 5. Ni_3Sn_4/Ni_3P thickness ratio versus P concentration of electroless $Ni-P$ UBM showing good prediction by equation (8). References to the experimental results are shown in the plot.

As one may see, the comparison is quite good **only if** one does not try to include the voids volume into the volume of the spongy layer " Ni_3P +voids". Indeed, the volume of the voids (**if one neglects the relaxation of empty spaces**)

$$V(\text{void}) = \frac{f}{1-f} V(Ni_3P) = \frac{1-4c}{4} \frac{(3M_{Ni}+M_P)}{\rho_{Ni_3P}} v, \quad (9a)$$

$$V(Ni_3P) + V(\text{void}) = \frac{1}{4} \frac{(3M_{Ni}+4M_{Sn})}{\rho_{Ni_3Sn_4}} v. \quad (9b)$$

Then the ratio of Ni_3Sn_4 thickness and the **whole spongy** Ni_3P layer will be

$$\frac{V(Ni_3Sn_4)}{V(Ni_3P)+V(\text{void})} = \frac{\rho_{Ni_3P}(3M_{Ni}+4M_{Sn})}{\rho_{Ni_3Sn_4}(3M_{Ni}+M_P)} \frac{4(1-4c)}{3} \approx 4 \cdot (1 - 4c). \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) for the ratio of the volumes with voids, on average, fits experimental results worse than equation (8) for the ratio of the volumes without voids - say, at $c=0.125$ it gives a prediction two times less than the experimental result in Fig.5. Most

probably, it means that the fraction of voids is overestimated in our model - real voids may have less volume (1) due to voids volume relaxation, and (2) due to using the vacancy flux from these voids for the formation and growth of Ni_3Sn_4 and ternary Ni-Sn-P phases. On the other hand, ref.[23] gives from 2.3 to 2.7 and eq. (10) gives about 2, which seems not that bad (see also the prediction below from kinetic equations).

III. KINETIC EQUATIONS

Let us first write and solve the equation describing the interdiffusion of Ni and P along the interface between solution Ni(P) and compound Ni_3P , moving with some instant velocity V . In the frame of reference moving together with the mentioned interface of thickness δ , the basic equation for Ni out-diffusion is:

$$\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{int}}{\partial t} = \overline{D^{int}} \frac{\partial^2 C_{Ni}^{int}}{\partial y^2} - \frac{V}{\delta} (C_{Ni}^{int} - C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)}). \quad (11)$$

Last term in the right-hand side of eq. (11) is a flux divergence at the surface layer - difference between the incoming flux (from vapor) and outgoing flux into bulk, in respect to reference frame pinned to the moving surface of the deposited film.

We also assume that the process is controlled by diffusion rather than by reaction, so that the composition at the boundaries of corresponding intervals are determined by the local equilibrium conditions.

By introducing the first characteristic length parameter $\lambda_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\overline{D^{int}} \delta}{V}}$ and adopting the natural boundary condition in the center: $C_{Ni}^{int}(y=0) = C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} = 1 - c$, one gets the solution

$$C_{Ni}^{int}(y) = C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - A_1 \left(\cosh\left(\frac{y}{\lambda_1}\right) - 1 \right). \quad (12)$$

The constant A_1 can be found from the conservation of Ni atoms in an interval of $0 < y < \frac{a}{2}$:

$$-\overline{D^{int}} \frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{int}}{\partial y} \left(y = \frac{a}{2} \right) \cdot \delta \cdot W \cdot dt = (C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P}) \cdot \frac{a}{2} \cdot W \cdot V dt, \quad (13)$$

$$\text{so that } A_1 = \frac{a}{2\delta} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P})}{\sinh(a/2\lambda_1)} \cdot \frac{V \cdot \lambda_1}{\overline{D^{int}}} = \frac{a}{2\lambda_1} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P})}{\sinh(a/2\lambda_1)} \cdot \frac{V \cdot (\lambda_1)^2}{\delta \overline{D^{int}}} = \frac{a}{2\lambda_1} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P})}{\sinh(a/2\lambda_1)}. \quad (14)$$

Thus,

$$C_{Ni}^{int}(y) = C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - \frac{a}{2\lambda_1} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P})}{\sinh(a/2\lambda_1)} \left(\cosh\left(\frac{y}{\lambda_1}\right) - 1 \right). \quad (15)$$

Now let us first write and solve the equation describing the surface diffusion of Ni along the free surface of solution Ni(P) with a local void at the boundary, moving with the same instant velocity V. In the frame of reference moving together with the mentioned surface of thickness δ , the basic equation is:

$$\frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}{\partial t} = D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \frac{\partial^2 C_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}{\partial y^2} + \frac{V}{\delta} (1 - c - C_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}), \quad (16)$$

with boundary conditions

$$C_{Ni}^{surf}(y = \frac{a+b}{2}) = C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} = 1 - c, \quad (17)$$

$$-D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \frac{\partial C_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}{\partial y} (y = \frac{a}{2}) \cdot \delta \cdot W \cdot dt = (C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - 0) \cdot \frac{b}{2} \cdot W \cdot V dt \quad (18)$$

Then analogical algebra gives:

$$C_{Ni}^{surf}(y) = C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - \frac{b}{2\lambda_2} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)})}{\sinh(\frac{b}{2\lambda_2})} \left(\cosh\left(\frac{y - \frac{a+b}{2}}{\lambda_1}\right) - 1 \right), \quad \lambda_2 = \sqrt{\frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \delta}{V}} \quad (19)$$

To find a and b, we have two more conditions - conservation law and “sewing” condition of continuity at the boundary of two intervals:

$$C_{Ni}^{int}(y = \frac{a}{2} - 0) = C_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}(y = \frac{a}{2} + 0).$$

Thus,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{a}{2\lambda_1} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P})}{\sinh(a/2\lambda_1)} \left(\cosh\left(\frac{a}{2\lambda_1}\right) - 1 \right) = \frac{b}{2\lambda_2} \frac{(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)})}{\sinh(\frac{b}{2\lambda_2})} \left(\cosh\left(\frac{b}{2\lambda_2}\right) - 1 \right) \\ \frac{b}{a+b} = f = 1 - 4c \end{array} \right. \quad (20a,b)$$

In general, this set of equations can be solved only numerically, and the solution depends on two parameters - c (atomic fraction of P in Ni(P)) and the ratio of diffusion coefficients along the free surface of Ni(P) and along interface Ni(P)/Ni₃P ($\frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}{D_{Ni}^{int}}$):

$$\text{Let } \lambda_2/\lambda_1 = \sqrt{\frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}{D_{Ni}^{int}}} = 3, c=0.125, \text{ so that } f=0.5, a=b. \quad (21)$$

At that, $C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} = 1 - c = 0.875$, $(C_{Ni}^{Ni(P)} - C_{Ni}^{Ni_3P}) = 0.875 - 0.750 = 0.125$

We denote $x = \frac{a}{\lambda_1}$. Then a numeric solution of the transcendent equation

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sinh(x)}{\sinh(\frac{x}{3})} \cdot \frac{\cosh(\frac{x}{3}) - 1}{\cosh(x) - 1} - \frac{125}{875} = 0$$

has a unique positive root, approximately, $x=2.08$.

In this case, one gets

$$a = b = 2.08 \cdot \lambda_1 = 2.08 \sqrt{\frac{D^{int} \delta}{v}}. \quad (22)$$

As one could guess from the very beginning, the mean lateral grain size of hollow Ni_3P structure is inversely proportional to the velocity of transformation: the faster is transformation, the less is the lateral size - in full analogy, for example, with directional eutectic crystallization ($\lambda_1^2 V = const$) [39].

Now we should derive the expression for the velocity of the transformation front. We use the expressions for diffusion fluxes in the growing compounds with almost zero concentration range, in terms of mobilities or tracer diffusivities, and the driving forces Δg of compound formation (for details please look [40,41,12]). Namely, diffusion flux across the intermediate phase layer is determined by Fick's law, which means the product of average interdiffusion coefficient $\langle \widetilde{D}^{int} \rangle$ within compound's concentration range, and the width ΔC of this concentration range, and inversely proportional to the phase width ΔX^{Ni_3P} . Product $\langle \widetilde{D}^{int} \rangle \Delta C$ is often called "Wagner diffusivity" [42], where the concentration range width ΔC is typically very small and difficult for measuring, contrary to the thermodynamic driving force Δg of compound formation. It can be reduced ([40,41,12]) to the product of tracer diffusivity of faster component and the reduced thermodynamic driving force $\Delta g/kT$:

$$\langle \widetilde{D}^{int} \rangle \Delta C = D_{Ni}^{surf Ni(P)} \Delta g/kT$$

Conservation of matter means that that all "extra" nickel is removed via the surface diffusion:

$$[(1 - c) \cdot \frac{a+b}{2} - \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{a}{2}] \cdot W \cdot V dt = \frac{D_{Ni}^{surf Ni(P)} \Delta g/kT}{\Delta X^{Ni_3P}} dt \cdot \delta \cdot W, \quad (23)$$

so that

$$V = \frac{2\delta}{(a+b)} \frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g / kT}{(1-4c) \cdot \Delta X^{Ni_3P}}. \quad (24)$$

In this case, a and b are proportional to the square root of ΔX^{Ni_3P} ,

$$a=b= 2.08 \sqrt{\frac{\overline{D^{int}} \delta}{V}} = 2.08 \sqrt{\frac{(a+b) \overline{D^{int}} \delta (1-4c) \cdot \Delta X^{Ni_3P}}{2\delta D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g / kT}}. \quad (25)$$

Strictly speaking, nominator and denominator in eq.(25) contain different values of δ -effective width of interface "amorphous NiP/crystalline Ni_3P " and effective width of the free surface of newly formed compound Ni_3P . Approximately, we take them both

about 0.5 nm. again, as in eq. (21), we consider the case $\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} = \sqrt{\frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}{D_{Ni}^{int}}} = 3, c=0.125,$

so that $f=0.5, a=b$), which immediately gives

$$a = b = 4.33 \frac{\overline{D^{int}} (1-4c) \cdot \Delta X^{Ni_3P}}{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g / kT}, \quad (26)$$

$$V = \frac{\delta}{4.33} \frac{(D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g / kT)^2}{\overline{D^{int}} ((1-4c) \Delta X^{Ni_3P})^2}. \quad (27)$$

and the growth law will be determined by the exponent $\frac{1}{3}$ (see below eq. (34)) instead of the common parabolic exponent 0.5 .

Note that eq. (27) gives reasonable quantitative evaluation for the lateral grain size of Ni_3P : Indeed, $4.33 \frac{(1-4c)}{\Delta g / kT}$ is of the order 10^0 (about 1) for phosphorous content c

about 0.125. $\frac{\overline{D^{int}}}{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)}}$ is of the order of 10^{-1} since surface diffusion is always faster

than the diffusion along the interface between two solid phases. If ΔX^{Ni_3P} has a typical length of about 5 microns, the a and b should be about 10 times less (several hundred nanometers) which seems realistic looking at Figs. 1, 2.

Kinetics for other interfaces will be analyzed for the following specific case: Let us assume that the main and only diffusant in all phases is nickel: (1) in the layer of spongy Ni_3P the Ni atoms migrate via the inner free surfaces of Ni_3P grains; (2) in the

layer Ni_3Sn_4 the Ni migrates via the grain boundaries or via the liquid channels (if any) between the grains towards the reaction at the boundary with solder. In this case, we get the following kinetic equations:

The left boundary moves left consuming electroless Ni and converting part of it into spongy Ni_3P .

$$\frac{dy_{\alpha/(Ni_3P+void)}}{dt} = -V = \frac{2\delta}{(a+b)} \frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g/kT}{(1-4c)\Delta X^{Ni_3P}} = -\frac{\delta}{4.33} \frac{(D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g/kT)^2}{D^{int}((1-4c)\Delta X^{Ni_3P})^2}. \quad (28)$$

The rest of Ni, coming to the interface $(Ni_3P + void)/Ni_3Sn_4$, leaves this interface immobile and goes further (unchanged) via the Ni_3Sn_4 phase to react with Sn at its right boundary:

$$\frac{dy_{(Ni_3P+void)/Ni_3Sn_4}}{dt} = 0, \quad (29)$$

$$\Omega J_{Ni} = \Omega J_{Ni}(Ni_3P+void) = \frac{2\delta}{(a+b)} \frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g/kT}{\Delta X^{Ni_3P}} = \Omega J_{Ni}(Ni_3Sn_4) = \frac{D_{Wagner}^{Ni_3Sn_4}}{\Delta X^{Ni_3Sn_4}}, \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{dy_{Ni_3Sn_4/Sn}}{dt} = \frac{7}{3} \Omega J_{Ni} = \frac{7}{3} \frac{2\delta}{(a+b)} \frac{D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g/kT}{\Delta X^{Ni_3P}}. \quad (31)$$

Here $\Delta X^{Ni_3P} = y_{(Ni_3P+void)/Ni_3Sn_4} - y_{\alpha/(Ni_3P+void)}$,

$$\frac{d\Delta X^{Ni_3P}}{dt} = \frac{dy_{\alpha/(Ni_3P+void)}}{dt} = \frac{\delta}{4.33} \frac{(D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g/kT)^2}{D^{int}((1-4c)\Delta X^{Ni_3P})^2}, \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{d\Delta X^{Ni_3Sn_4}}{dt} \approx \frac{7}{3} \frac{d\Delta X^{Ni_3P}}{dt}. \quad (33)$$

so that $\frac{1}{3}$ (ripening-like) law should be valid:

$$(\Delta X^{Ni_3P})^3 = \frac{3\delta}{4.33} \frac{(D_{Ni}^{surfNi(P)} \Delta g/kT)^2}{D^{int}(1-4c)^2} \cdot t, \Rightarrow \Delta X^{Ni_3P} = const \cdot t^{1/n}, \quad n \cong 3. \quad (34)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta X^{Ni_3Sn_4} \approx 2.33 \cdot \Delta X^{Ni_3P}. \quad (35)$$

Both predictions (34,35) - time exponent about $\frac{1}{3}$ for the growth law and the ratio of phase thicknesses fit the experimental results of Kumar et al [23]:

(1) According to Table II in ref.[23] the average (over three temperatures) time exponent for the phase Ni_3P is 3.2, and for the phase Ni_3Sn_4 - 3.1 (compare $n = 3$ in eq. (34)) - we believe this correspondence is satisfactory.

(2) According to Table I in ref. [23], the average ratio $\Delta X^{Ni_3Sn_4}/\Delta X^{Ni_3P}$ practically coincides with late stages of solid-state aging at 180 °C (2.3 against theoretical 2.33),

differs by about 13-17 % at 160 °C and 140 °C (2,6-2.7 against 2.33), and does not fit at all at 200 °C (3-6 against 2.33). We believe the discrepancy is related mainly to the formation and growth of the ternary phase and with using part of voids within Ni_3P for vacancy flux across the ternary phase and Ni_3Sn_4 phase generating the additional Sn flux to the reaction front.

Another marginal case is if within Ni_3P spongy phase only Ni is mobile along free surfaces, and within Ni_3Sn_4 - only Sn is mobile. In this case, the intermediate ternary phase is necessary for matter balance.

IV. MONTE CARLO SIMULATION OF FDDP

We suggest a rather simple illustrative 2D simulation of the FDDP (Flux-Driven Discontinuous Precipitation). Let us consider 2D-alloy AB with triangular lattice with interactions within two coordination shells, with negative mixing energy $E_{mix}^I < 0$ between nearest neighbors and positive mixing energy $E_{mix}^{II} > 0$ between next nearest neighbors. In such a system, one expects two ordered intermediate phases A_2B_1 and A_1B_2 at sufficiently low temperature. In an ideally ordered stoichiometric phase A_2B each atom B is surrounded by 6 A-atoms, and each A-atom is surrounded by 3 atoms A and 3 atoms B. We introduce an initial vacancy row between two regions of 2D solid solutions with composition, say, $C_B=0.1$ (Fig. 6a) and mimic the out-flux of majority atoms A by just removing them from the boundaries solid region/empty region. Experimentally, we know that Ni atoms are removed from the metastable amorphous solution but not removed from the compound Ni_3P . Therefore, in our illustrative model, we introduced the threshold energy of the A-atom, below which it cannot be taken out. In our modeling, we took the following parameters:

$$\frac{\Phi_{AA}^I}{k_B T} = 0, \quad \frac{\Phi_{BB}^I}{k_B T} = 0, \quad \frac{\Phi_{AB}^I}{k_B T} = \frac{E_{mix}^I}{k_B T} = -0.7$$

$$\frac{\Phi_{AA}^{II}}{k_B T} = 0, \quad \frac{\Phi_{BB}^{II}}{k_B T} = 0, \quad \frac{\Phi_{AB}^{II}}{k_B T} = \frac{E_{mix}^{II}}{k_B T} = +0.7$$

$$\frac{E_{\text{threshold}}}{k_B T} = -0.8 \text{ (if A atom has at least two neighboring vacancies and the energy}$$

of this atom is larger than (or equal to) $E_{\text{threshold}}$, then this atom can be taken out to

the out-flux of A). Simultaneously, ordering of the region without vacancies may proceed by exchange mechanism and is realized by the Glauber algorithm, in which the energy of each atom interactions is calculated within two coordination shells. A number of exchange attempts per one attempt of A-atom withdrawal at the boundary void/solid solution is a main fitting parameter. In our illustrative model, we are not interested in the migration of A atom after its removal (in reality the removed Ni atoms should diffuse along the surfaces Ni_3P /void to react with Sn with the formation of Ni_3Sn_4 phase or Ni-Sn-P ternary phase).

An example of the stages of spongy ordered phase A_2B formation generated by the outflux of majority atoms, is shown in Fig.6. The protuberances (elongated voids) are growing from the initial boundaries in both directions simultaneously with the ordering of the remaining solid solution.

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIG.6. Formation and evolution of the sponge-like ordered phase with elongated voids due to out-flux of majority A-atoms (A-red, B- blue).

Conclusions.

1. Elongated voids formation simultaneously with the formation and growth of bamboo-like Ni_3P grains can be explained and self-consistently described as flux-driven cellular precipitation caused by the out-flux of nickel for reaction with tin-based solder. Predictions (20-28) of lateral grain sizes provide reasonable sub-micron values.
2. Prediction of phase volume ratio for growing phases Ni_3Sn_4 and Ni_3P (eq. (8)) seems quite reasonable, but predictions of the void fraction (Eq. (2, 9, 10)) seem exaggerated - maybe, the actual void fraction is lower (1) due to some relaxation effects, (2) due to vacancy out-flux from the voids into Ni-Sn-P and Ni_3Sn_4 phase layers, generating the Sn flux to react with incoming Ni.
3. The kinetic model, so far, was suggested only for the case when Ni is the main diffusant in both growing phases. This model predicts the power law 1/3 for the growth of both phases Ni_3Sn_4 and Ni_3P (Eqs. (34, 35)), which fits the experimental data [5].
4. The illustrative 2D-Monte Carlo model supports the main idea of the FDDP concept - simultaneous voiding and ordering when the chemical driving force acting on the majority atoms component, is sufficient to take out the majority atoms from still disordered phase but is insufficient to take out majority atoms from the ordered phase.

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5. Emergence, the evolution of the ternary phase between Ni_3Sn_4 and Ni_3P , as well as phase competition in the ternary system, will be discussed elsewhere.
 6. An approach suggested in this paper, may be useful for further developing the dealloying theory.

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